

ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT AND CLASSIFICATION OF PUBLIC EVENTS

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In the article, public events, their types, public events concept and its classification are scientifically and theoretically analyzed.

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Public order and safety during public events in the world remains a constant focus of attention of the state, public organizations and citizens, the trend of holding public events is increasing, and in particular, the fact that mass disturbances have occurred during these events in a number of countries is urgent. remains one of the problems.

Russian scientists N.Yu. According to Shvedova and one of our national scientists, M.X.Rustambayev, "a rally is a meeting of a group gathered to discuss political issues ¹. " However, this definition given by scientists cannot adequately reveal the essence of the "rally" concept, gaining general importance. For this reason, different definitions have been given to this concept by other scientists. Can be of demand, goodwill (support) or protest. has touched on ². Although the definition reveals a number of aspects of this concept , it cannot be fully agreed to because it does not take into account that the rally can be held in the form of a reaction to the actions of an official or organization.

On the contrary, Yu.I. Fedinsky, A.Ya. In the opinion of other Russian scientists such as Sukharyova, VE Krutskikh, "a rally is the reaction of citizens to the actions of an official person

¹Толковый словарь русского языка с включением сведений о происхождении слов / РАН. Институт русского языка им. В.В. Виноградова, Отв. ред. Н.Ю. Шведова. – М., 2011: Издательский центр «Азбуковник». – С. 451.; Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституциясини ўрганиш: Бакалавриятнинг ноюрidik йўналишлари учун ўқув қўлланма. – Т.: "Ўзбекистон" 2001. – В. 186.; Ўзбекистон Республикасининг конституциявий ҳуқуқи. Масъул муҳаррир: ю.ф.д., проф. А.Х. Саидов. – Т.: ТДЮИ нашриёти, 2005. – В. 228.

²А.Б. Барихин. Большая юридическая энциклопедия. (Серия «Профессиональные справочники и энциклопедии») – М.: Книжный мир, 2010. – С. 456.; Ожегов С.И. Толковый словарь русского языка: Ок. 100 000 слов, терминов и фразеологических выражений / С.И.Ожегов; Под ред. Проф. Л.И.Скворцова. – 26-е изд., испр. и доп. – М.: ООО «Издательство Оникс»; ООО «Издательство «Мир и Образование», 2010. – С. 296.; Ушаков Д.Н. Толковый словарь современного русского языка, Д.Н.Ушаков – М.: «Аделант», 2013. – С. 303.

or organization on important social and political issues" ³, and the opinions of the above scientists were not taken into account in the definition given by them. we can see and partially agree with this definition.

In addition, Uzbek scientist U.Sh. According to Husainov: "a rally is a type of meeting held in the open air , usually in such public speeches, the organizers and its participants send a resolution to the government officials or citizens with some demands" ⁴.

When talking about the concept of "meeting" directly, it is mentioned in the legal encyclopedia of Uzbekistan that "meeting is an English expression , in Uzbek, it is held to solve some important event, political, socio-economic issues. is a gathering. "Rally " means that a certain political group or mass movement or production organizations, unions, who are usually in a festive mood or are dissatisfied with the state authorities, go to the city centers and express their opinions ⁵and demands .

According to the above general definition, Russian scientists AB Barikhin, AB Borisov, SI Ojegov, N.Yu. According to Shvedova, DN Ushakov, and the manual "Priority principles for conducting peaceful assemblies" developed by the OSCE Bureau for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights, "the assembly is a citizen's opinion on an issue" gathering in one place" ⁶cannot fully reveal the meaning of the concept of "gathering".

According to one of the Uzbek scientists, MX Rustambayev, "a meeting is a meeting of certain gathered persons held in a closed building or a room. Meetings in the form of majlis may be chosen by the organizers of the majlis to limit the number of participants, but this does not

³Большой толковый словарь официальных терминов: Более 8000 терминов / Сост. Ю.И. Фединский. - М.: ООО «Издательство Астрель»: ООО «Издательство АСТ», ООО «Транзиткнига», 2004. – С. 454.; Большой юридический словарь / Под ред. А.Я. Сухарева, В.Е. Крутских. – М.: ИНФРА–М. 2000. – В. 335.

⁴Xorijiy mamlakatlar konstitutsiyaviy huquqi: darslik / Mas'ul muharrir: prof. A.A.Azizxo`jayev: - T.: TDYI nashriyoti, 2010. – В. 139.

⁵Ўзбекистон юридик энциклопедияси / Нашр учун масъул Р.А. Мухитдинов ва бошқ.; масъул мухаррир Н. Тойчиев. – Т.: Адолат, 2009. – В. 310.

⁶А.Б.Барихин. Большая юридическая энциклопедия. (Серия «Профессиональные справочники и энциклопедии») – М.: Книжный мир, 2010. – С. 777.; Борисов А.Б. Большой юридический словарь. – М.: Книжный мир, 2010. – С. 686.; Ожегов С.И. Толковый словарь русского языка: Ок. 100 000 слов, терминов и фразеологических выражений / С.И.Ожегов; Под ред. Проф. Л.И.Скворцова. – 26-е изд., испр. и доп. – М.: ООО «Издательство Оникс»; ООО «Издательство «Мир и Образование», 2010. – С. 593.; Толковый словарь русского языка с включением сведений о происхождении слов / РАН. Институт русского языка им. В.В. Виноградова, Отв. ред. Н. Ю. Шведова. – М., 2011: Издательский центр «Азбуковник». – С. 909.; Ушаков Д.Н. Толковый словарь современного русского языка, Д.Н.Ушаков – М.: «Аделант», 2013. – С. 636.; Руководящие принципы по свободе мирных собраний. Издание 2-е / Опубликовано БДИПЧ ОБСЕ, 2011. – С. 139..

determine the main nature of the meeting ⁷. However, Russian scientists A.Ya. Sukhareva, VE Krutskikh said that the meetings can be held in the open air in addition to the building or closed places ⁸.

Although the opinions presented by the above scholars are considered complementary, aspects related to the place of the meetings are noted, but the meetings attract the attention of local authorities, state bodies, and the public, because it is not intended to judge the actions (inaction) of individuals, agencies and organizations and for other purposes, it cannot be completely joined.

In addition, according to the legislation of the Russian Federation, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan and the Republic of Belarus, "a meeting is a joint participation of citizens in order to discuss socially important issues, as well as the actions or inactions of individuals, agencies and organizations in a specially designated and equipped place." ⁹, - defined as.

it is defined that "a meeting is a gathering of citizens to discuss some socially important issue in order to attract the attention of the public, regional authorities and state bodies" ¹⁰.

Also, although it does not have any legal status, the decisions made by its participants are recorded as a proposal to the president 11. 72nd Anniversary of Victory in the War of Resistance Gathering¹² and analyzing a number of such gathering actions and the definitions given above, in our opinion, the concept of gathering should be defined as follows, that is, gathering - attracting the attention of local authorities, state bodies and the public joint participation of citizens in

⁷Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституциясини ўрганиш: Бакалавриятнинг ноюрidik йуналишлари учун укув кулланма. – Т.: "Ўзбекистон" 2001. – В. 186.; Ўзбекистон Республикасининг конституциявий ҳуқуқи. Масъул муҳаррир: ю.ф.д., проф. А.Х.Саидов. – Т.: ТДЮИ нашриёти, 2005. – В. 228.

⁸Большой юридический словарь / Под ред. А.Я. Сухарева, В.Е. Крутских. – М.: ИНФРА-М. 2000. – С. 565.

⁹Федеральный Закон Российской Федерации № 54-ФЗ "О собраниях, митингах, демонстрациях, шествиях и пикетированиях" от 19 июня 2004 года (с изменениями на 17 мая 2021 года). Статья 2.; Закон Республики Казахстан № 333-VI ЗРК "О порядке организации и проведения мирных собраний в Республике Казахстан" от 25 мая 2020 года. Статья 1.; Закон Туркменистана "Об организации и проведении собраний, митингов, демонстраций и других массовых мероприятий" от 28 февраля 2015 года (С изменениями внесенным Законами Туркменистана от 09.06.2018 г. № 38-VI и 14.03.2020 г. № 234-VI). Статья 1; Закон Республики Беларусь № 114-З "О массовых мероприятиях от 30 декабря 1997 года. Статья 2.

¹⁰Закон Кыргызской Республики № 64 "О мирных собраниях" от 23 мая 2012 года. Статья 3.; Закон Республики Таджикистан № 1169 "О собраниях, митингах, демонстрациях и уличных шествиях" от 31 декабря 2014 года. Статья № 1.

¹¹В Минске стартует Всебелорусское народное собрание [Elektron manba] // URL: <https://www.rbc.ru/politics/11/02/2021/602298d09a79477d0e7cb001> (murojaat etilgan vaqt 20.01.2022 y.)

¹²В Нанкине прошло международное мирное собрание, посвященное 72-летию победы в войне Сопротивления японским захватчикам [Elektron manba] // URL: <http://russian.people.com.cn/n3/2017/0816/c31516-9255808.html> (murojaat etilgan vaqt 20.01.2022 y.)

order to discuss issues of social importance, as well as actions or inactions of individuals, agencies and organizations, in a specially designated place without using propaganda materials.

Russian scientists DN Ushakov and N.Yu. According to Shvedova , "a picket is a type of demonstration organized by a group of citizens in order to express their demands or grievances without transferring its employees to an organization"¹³. This definition is "picket " does not fully reveal the concept.

At this point, Yu.I. The definition given by Fedinsky: "picketing should be carried out in a fixed place, that is, without moving along the route and without using sound-amplifying devices" U.Sh. ¹⁴By Husainov: "a picket is usually a situation of a small group of people (sometimes one person) sitting, standing or moving around some object with posters and transparencies" ¹⁵-enriched in terms of content.

In addition, according to the legislation of the Russian Federation, a picket is a public expression of the opinions of one or more citizens using posters, banners and other visual propaganda materials, as well as quick assembly constructions, without motion and without the use of sound-amplifying technical means in front of the object where the picket is held. highlighted as a form of ¹⁶.

According to the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan, "picket" is a group of citizens of the Republic of Kazakhstan at a certain time in a certain place without motion and without sound-amplifying equipment, as well as with or without the use of posters, banners and other propaganda materials. and (or) actions (inaction) of bodies, organizations, or expressing public opinion on socially important issues ¹⁷" we can see that it is reflected as a meeting in a certain place in order to express their opinions .¹⁸

¹³Ушаков Д.Н. Толковый словарь современного русского языка, Д.Н.Ушаков – М.: «Аделант», 2013. – С. 454.; Толковый словарь русского языка с включением сведений о происхождении слов / РАН. Институт русского языка им. В. В. Виноградова, Отв. ред. Н. Ю. Шведова. – М., 2011: Издательский центр «Азбуковник». – С. 643.

¹⁴Большой толковый словарь официальных терминов: Более 8000 терминов / Сост. Ю.И. Фединский. - М.: ООО «Издательство Астрель»: ООО «Издательство АСТ», ООО «Транзиткнига», 2004. – С. 622.

¹⁵Xorijiy mamlakatlar konstitutsiyaviy huquqi: darslik / Mas'ul muharrir: prof. A.A.Azizxo`jayev: - T.: TDYI nashriyoti, 2010. – B. 139.

¹⁶Федеральный Закон Российской Федерации № 54-ФЗ “О собраниях, митингах, демонстрациях, шествиях и пикетированиях” от 19 июня 2004 года (с изменениями на 17 мая 2021 года). Статья 2.; Закон Республики Казахстан № 333-VI ЗРК “О порядке организации и проведения мирных собраний в Республике Казахстан” от 25 мая 2020 года. Статья 1.

¹⁷Закон Республики Казахстан № 2126 «О порядке организации и проведения мирных собраний, митингов, шествий, пикетов и демонстраций в Республике Казахстан» от 17 марта 1995 года. Статья 1.

¹⁸Закон Азербайджанской Республики “О свободе собраний” № 537-ПГ от 13 ноября 1998 г. Статья 2.

In addition, when a picket is held by one person, he has the status of both a participant and an organizer at the same time. At this point, in our opinion, it is reasonable to consider the person who wants to hold a one-man picket as an organizer, taking into account that this person has interests in holding a picket, that he is the initiator of the picket.

Russian scientists Yu.I. Fedinsky, A.Ya. According to Sukharyova and VE Krutskikh, "street marches are mass movements along the pedestrian and car traffic section of the road with the aim of drawing the attention of authorities and the public to some socially important issue¹⁹. " This definition does not fully cover the concept of " street marches".

Among Uzbek scientists, U.Sh. Husainov's opinion that " street marches can also be in the form of marches, and they can be held across settlements, even the whole country or several countries"²⁰ broadens the meaning of the concept of "street marches".

Of Tajikistan and Belarus, "street marches are movements along a predetermined route in order to attract the attention of authorities and the public to a problem, and also public opinion on social and political issues. can also aim to inform"²¹.

According to the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan, "street marches can be carried out without vehicles and sound amplifiers, transparent and other propaganda materials can be used²². "

Analyzing the above definitions, we agree that it is possible to draw public attention to issues of social importance from street processions, express public opinion on problems, and conduct street marches in the form of a procession.

In recent times, flash mobs on socio-political issues have appeared as a type of mass event. According to the OSCE Office for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights, the "Priority Principles for Peaceful Assemblies" guide: "a flash mob is a group of people who gather together, perform a series of actions and quickly It is defined as a short-term mass movement with the spread, and these movements embody the element of surprise²³.

¹⁹Большой толковый словарь официальных терминов: Более 8000 терминов / Сост. Ю.И. Фединский. - М.: ООО «Издательство Астрель»: ООО «Издательство АСТ», ООО «Транзиткнига», 2004. – С. 923.; Большой юридический словарь / Под ред. А.Я. Сухарева, В.Е. Крутских. – М.: ИНФРА–М. 2000. – С. 683.

²⁰Xorijiy mamlakatlar konstitutsiyaviy huquqi: darslik / Mas'ul muharrir: prof. A.A.Azizxo`jayev: - T.: TDYI nashriyoti, 2010. – B. 139.

²¹Закон Республики Таджикистан № 1169 “О собраниях, митингах, демонстрациях и уличных шествиях” от 31 декабря 2014 года. Статья № 1.; Закон Республики Беларусь № 114-З “О массовых мероприятиях от 30 декабря 1997 года. Статья 2.

²²Закон Республики Казахстан № 333-VI ЗРК “О порядке организации и проведения мирных собраний в Республике Казахстан” от 25 мая 2020 года. Статья 1.

²³Руководящие принципы по свободе мирных собраний. Издание 2-е / Опубликовано БДИПЧ ОБСЕ, 2011. – С. 156.

see that there are a number of types of flash mobs today . For example: artmob (certain advertising campaigns with artistic value); with dance (music from the dance is played among the public, and the participants perform a collective dance prepared in advance); extreme-mob (extreme actions are carried out among the public, in which moral principles may be violated, petty hooliganism, offenses against random passers-by may be committed); L-mob (a type of flash mob that lasts for a long time (up to a week) based on a script set by the participants at a convenient time); Farshing (participants perform performances deviating from normal psychological, moral and social norms, including unusual actions such as men dancing in women's clothes, throwing food, breaking their own telephones); fan-mob (type of flashmob that causes public joy); mob-house (performed by playing a life process, not a script, for the time set by the participants); i-mob (type of flashmob carried out on Internet networks); politmob or sociomob (a movement dedicated to social or political issues, and a simple, fast and safe way to express public opinion about rallies or demonstrations or draw attention to certain problems)²⁴.

In conclusion, we emphasize that it is important to distinguish them from each other in the proper organization of public events, as well as to know the specific aspects of each event. Conducting these events is one of the basic political rights of citizens to solve social and political problems, to express their position on important issues, to support the actions (inaction) of any person, organization or state bodies, or to express their dissatisfaction with them. remains one.

²⁴Р.Жантасов. Флешмобы – права на свободу выражения мнений. Техническое задание по итогам тренинга «Исследования и мониторинг в области прав человека», Алматы, 2018. – С. 10. [Elektron manba] // URL: https://www.soros.kz/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/ZHANTASOV_web_.pdf (murojaat etilgan vaqt 25.01.2022 y.)